

**OLANZAPINE-INDUCED HYPERPROLACTINEMIA WITH GYNECOMASTIA IN A
MALE PATIENT: A CASE REPORT*****Dr. Mohammed Shefeeq A., Pharm D.**

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ABSTRACT

Hyperprolactinemia is a known adverse effect of antipsychotics, though clinically significant prolactin elevation with olanzapine is uncommon. A 31-year-old male with chronic psychosis on long-term olanzapine therapy, presented with worsening psychotic symptoms following medication non-adherence. Examination revealed gynecomastia, elevated serum prolactin, and mild diffuse cerebral atrophy in CT imaging. The patient showed clinical improvement with normalization of prolactin levels on substitution of the drug with Aripiprazole. This case highlights a rare presentation of hyperprolactinemia occurring in a male patient during long-term olanzapine therapy, a condition more typically associated with short-term treatment and switching to a prolactin-sparing antipsychotic such as aripiprazole can be an effective management strategy.

KEYWORDS: Examination revealed gynecomastia, elevated serum prolactin, and mild diffuse cerebral atrophy in CT imaging.**INTRODUCTION**

Psychosis is a mental health condition characterized by a loss of contact with reality, resulting in distorted thoughts, perceptions, and interpretations of the environment, which gradually decreases their quality of life. Psychotherapy and psychopharmacotherapy are the two ways to manage psychosis wherein; psychotherapy there are individual, behavioral, social and cognitive therapies that can be implemented and in psychopharmacotherapy antipsychotics are used. These antipsychotics have a trade-off between reducing the psychotic symptoms and causing adverse effects. These adverse effects are variable depending upon the type of classification; second-generation (atypical) antipsychotics are more frequently associated with metabolic syndrome, while first-generation (typical) antipsychotics are predominantly linked to movement disorders.^[1] Overall adverse effects can range from mild sedation, dry mouth to extrapyramidal symptoms such as dyskinesia, akathisia along with sexual dysfunction, postural hypertension, cardiac related risk or death. Adverse effect of hyperprolactinemia was observed in this patient during Olanzapine therapy.

CASE REPORT

A 31 year old unmarried male patient, educated up to upper primary not gainfully employed from a rural background with well-adjusted premorbid personality and with history of Intellectual Development Disorder presented to general health psychiatry unit with the chief complaints of suspicion that others are trying to harm him and are poisoning his food, muttering to self, decreased sleep at night. The patient was diagnosed with chronic psychosis and was on treatment since 12 years. Olanzapine 10 mg twice a day was prescribed for last 10 years and the symptoms exacerbated over the past 8 months due to non-adherence to medication.

Further examination during the hospitalization revealed gynecomastia, for which prolactin levels were assessed. The patient's prolactin level was elevated at 36.39 ng/mL, exceeding the normal reference range (6.0–29.9 ng/mL). A computed tomography (CT) scan of the brain showed mild diffuse cerebral atrophy. Due to increase in prolactin levels and inability to respond to the treatment with olanzapine, the drug was tapered and stopped. Aripiprazole therapy was initiated at 10 mg and titrated to 20 mg daily, along with amisulpride 50mg for the

negative symptoms. The patient was discharged after resolution of hyperprolactinemia (prolactin: 14.6 ng/ml) on aripiprazole for continued management and closely monitored the prolactin levels during the stay due to concomitant administration of amisulpride.

DISCUSSION

This report describes a case of olanzapine-induced hyperprolactinemia in a male patient, treated for psychosis with the drug for more than a decade, showing that adverse effect occurred after a chronic use. Olanzapine, an atypical antipsychotic with proven efficacy against both positive and negative symptoms of schizophrenia, is widely used in other psychotic disorders. Various guidelines recommend it as a first line drug for psychosis at minimal effective dose. It acts on dopamine and serotonin receptors by blocking dopamine (D_2) receptors in the mesolimbic pathway and acting as an antagonist to 5-HT_{2A} receptors in frontal cortex, hence showing a decrease in both positive and negative symptoms. Importantly, olanzapine binds loosely to the D_2 receptor and dissociates easily allowing for near-normal dopamine neurotransmission.^[2]

A multiple regression analysis assessing five second-generation antipsychotics found that risperidone and olanzapine treatments increased plasma prolactin levels, while aripiprazole reduced it, and perospirone and quetiapine showed no effect.^[3] Olanzapine demonstrated a dose-dependent increase of prolactin in a study.^[4]

Hyperprolactinemia is a commonly caused side effect of neuroleptic agents, but olanzapine-induced prolactin elevation is rare, particularly in male patients. Antipsychotics induced hyperprolactinemia results from D_2 receptors, which block the lactotroph cells from producing prolactin hormone by binding on its membrane. Dopamine normally inhibits prolactin secretion; but the antagonism of D_2 receptor leads to loss of this inhibitory control and subsequent elevation. Extent of the rise largely depends on rate of dissociation of the drug from the D_2 receptor: faster dissociation is associated with less prolactin elevation. This distinction

allows antipsychotics to be classified into prolactin-raising (conventional neuroleptics, amisulpride, risperidone) and prolactin-sparing (clozapine, aripiprazole, olanzapine).^[5]

High-performance liquid chromatography analysis has shown that olanzapine's brain penetration is limited by P-glycoprotein (P-gp), an efflux transporter located at the blood-brain barrier and other tissues. Functional polymorphisms of P-gp may cause interindividual variability in the therapeutic efficacy and side effect profile, including susceptibility to hyperprolactinemia.^[6]

Patients at the risk of hyperprolactinemia due to antipsychotics need periodic prolactin monitoring along with the evaluation of bone mineral density, as sustained prolactin elevation may lead to hypogonadism. Aripiprazole or other prolactin sparing atypical antipsychotics are effective alternatives in persistent elevation^[7], as aripiprazole demonstrated reasonable effectiveness and safety for managing antipsychotic-induced hyperprolactinemia in a meta-analysis.^[8]

In this case, there was no baseline plasma prolactin level, as they were obtained only for the assessment of the symptoms during the present hospitalization. Although several guidelines advise measuring prolactin prior to starting the treatment, it is often regarded as optional rather than mandatory due to the lack of consensus. Difference in clinical practice and possibly a lack of awareness of this problem among physicians may contribute to under-monitoring. Given that patient with severe mental illness receive long-term antipsychotic therapy, it is essential to monitor for potential risks. Prolactin levels should be measured at the start of treatment, even if early symptoms such as amenorrhea or galactorrhea are not observed, to avoid underestimating other symptoms that may appear later.^[9]

Naranjo adverse drug reaction probability assessment yielded a score of 6 as shown in the Table, indicating a 'probable' association.

Table: Naranjo algorithm for adverse reaction causality assessment. Score categories are as follows adverse drug reaction is definite ≥ 9 ; probable 5-8; possible 1-4; doubtful 0.

Sr. No.	Questions	yes	no	don't know	score
1	Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	1	0	0	1
2	Did the adverse event appear after the suspected drug was administered?	2	-1	0	2
3	Did the adverse event improve when the drug was discontinued or a specific antagonist was administered?	1	0	0	1
4	Did the adverse event reappear when the drug was readministered?	2	-1	0	0
5	Are there alternative causes that could on their own have caused the reaction?	-1	2	0	0
6	Did the reaction reappear when a placebo was given?	-1	1	0	1
7	Was the drug detected in blood or other fluids in	1	0	0	0

	concentrations known to be toxic?				
8	Was the reaction more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	1	0	0	0
9	Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	1	0	0	0
10	Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	1	0	0	1

On comparison of acute and long-term effect of olanzapine against haloperidol (a typical antipsychotic) and placebo on serum prolactin concentrations, Haloperidol groups showed higher incidences of treatment emergent prolactin elevation in a trial. Olanzapine, even at the highest doses tested, was not associated with persistent elevations of prolactin, consistent with an 'atypical' pharmacologic profile, making this case less common.^[10]

Interestingly, another study reported that olanzapine significantly decreased the serum prolactin level in patients with schizophrenia, with a more pronounced effect in males. The study also reported a correlation between the improvement in positive symptoms and the change in serum prolactin level before and after olanzapine treatment, and suggested to use the serum prolactin level as a biological marker for predicting the therapeutic response.^[11]

This case highlights the need for a large-sample study of patients receiving chronic olanzapine therapy to obtain statistically significant evidence regarding its metabolic effects and the role of genetic polymorphisms on its pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics.

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